

PERFORMANCE INCREASING STUDIES WITHIN THE VALUE CHAIN STAGES IN THE OIL INDUSTRY

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Abstract

Purpose – To present the way of using the performance indicators within the value chain stages in case of the oil companies.

Methodology/approach – In order to perform the research, it was used the step-by-step multiple regression analysis, part of the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences - SPSS software. The research methodology was a survey-based questionnaire, the obtained data being processed using the SPSS program, version 23.

Findings – Description of the key activities performed by the oil companies; performance indicators presentation; analyzing the correlations between performance indicators and presenting the regression equation for the main value chain stages.

Research limitations/implications – Difficulties to access specific oil industry related data; no option to use for the research new indicators out of the existing ones; lack of an open oil industry related database.

Practical implications – The main importance of the analysis consists in the functionality of the model, with applicability in case of any other oil company with a similar activity profile.

Originality/value – Presentation of the main oil industry specific activities and performance indicators used in the value chain's stages; and the ranking of the main oil value chain stages based on the importance resulting from the answers processed in the research.

Key words: performance, oil industry.

Introduction

The concept of "value chain" has received major significance in the context of the world economies' globalization. Its importance has grown with the development of technologies and the increasing pace of modernization of factories and production units.

The companies' desire to gain market share, to surpass competition, respectively to have a competitive advantage in the market in which they operate, required a more flexible and much more efficient way of organizing their business processes than in the past (Michael Porter, 1985). Thus, each type of activity should be viewed from the perspective of its contribution to the total added value, so that, to help the performance improvement within the value chain stages.

Within oil companies, one of the most important aspect is related to the operational continuity, without interruption along the supply chain stages, emphasizing the process optimization efforts by using the synergies of the main and support activities. Specifically to the oil companies is the fact that for certain activities they could use their own resources or could appeal to outsourced resources as well (which is a trend more and more common in current practice in case of the "non-core businesses"); or they could rely on experts' involvement by contracting specialized services.

The oil business is and will remain an engine of the global economy, so performance researches will add value to the working processes, contributing to the companies' performance increasing. Being part

of the doctoral thesis, this research aims both to highlight the current state of knowledge of performance measurement in the oil industry and to identify the current state of use of performance indicators based on which the management of oil companies could evaluate performance along the value chain stages.

Main objectives of the study

In order to perform the practical research, it was necessary to establish specific main and secondary objectives, these being presented in figure 1.

Figure 1. The research's main and secondary objectives

In the first part of the research, was introduced and debated the notion of performance, respectively were discussed the value chain related concepts both from a historical and from the modern theory perspective. Different risk elements within the value chain were also mentioned, highlighting the importance to ensure the business continuity without any process interruption during the day-by-day operations.

The inclusion of risk elements in the research is a recognition of the importance of this aspect. With all precautions, however, accidents can occur during the value chain stages. They occur as a result of a certain critical risk factor, or due to several non-major risk factors that together trigger an event which might cause a disruption in the supply chain. In this sense, unintended risks could have technological or process reason, respectively they may be caused by human error.

As the performance of companies is directly influenced by ensuring a continuous activity, it was necessary to address the non-fragmentation aspects of the business. This risk can occur due to two factors, which are delays and interruptions in the value chain.

Delays usually appear when the company is unable to respond to a series of unforeseen events that have occurred in the company's internal or external environment and could have causes, such as:

- lack of raw materials;
- manufacturing defects;
- fluctuations or breakdowns of utilities;
- unannounced controls and inspections;
- bad weather conditions;
- lack of well-specialized staff;
- customs procedures, authorizations, etc.

Interruptions appear along the supply chain, as a result of very serious events, which generally have a rare but unpredictable frequency and with devastating effects for the company, such as:

- blocking a company's accounts;
- withdrawal of operating permits or licenses;
- calamities and natural disasters;
- strikes and revolutions;
- acts of terrorism and sabotage, etc.

As a result of the negative effects, both in case of delays and in case of interruptions, the companies' management have tried to find solutions and methods to manage these delays.

Because the evaluation of the companies' results is performed based on calculations, it was necessary to appeal and study the specific literature regarding the activity monitoring methods by using the key performance indicators.

The oil industry is influenced both by the current legislation, but also by the new consumer's trend that tries to promote a healthy, safe and green technology and culture, as well. Despite all the efforts made by the various groups interested in promoting green energy, the classic technology, based on hydrocarbons, is the most used, having a major impact on the world's economy. The value chain related to this business model is also well defined, and the performance of this chain could make the difference between the companies' success or failure. Therefore, the usage of the key performance indicators is undoubtedly necessary, and large oil companies have developed their own ways of monitoring, controlling and reporting their activity.

The objective of the research could be achieved only by identifying the performance indicators used in the stages of the value chain in the oil industry, the indicators being presented in the table no.1.

Table 1. Key Performance Indicators used within the supply chain stages

Primary (basic) activities		
Supply Chain stages	Activities	Indicators
Inbound Logistics	Transportation planning	Truck Loading Grade (TLG)
		Average km per truck (Av km)
		Average trucks no. used per day (AVTno)
	Reception of goods	Unloading discrepancies (ULD)
	Storage and Warehousing	Storage Tank Loading Grade (STLG)
		Tank turns (TT)
Inventory management	Inventory discrepancies (Sf)	
Operations	Producție și activități administrative	No. of orders processed (PO)
		Fuels throughput (FT)
		Losses (LS)
Outbound Logistics	Terminal operations	Truck Loading Gantry Utilization (TLGU)
		Storage Days (SD)
	Transportation, grouping and distribution	Entry-Exit Time (EET)
		Out of Product (OOP)
		Out of Stock (OOS)
		Daily truck no. (DTN)
Daily loading quantities (DLQ)		
Marketing and Sales	Data and market research	Finding market niches
		Selecting the right sales & promotion channels
		Defining product-price promotion policy
		Retail operations management
		Customer and competitors' data analysis
		Market share monitoring
Service and Maintenance	Service and repairs	No. of unscheduled repairs (URep)
		No. of unscheduled repairs hours (HUR)
		Maintenance time (MT)
	Training and Testing	Training & Acceptance (TA)

Support (secondary) activities		
Supply Chain stages	Activities	Indicators
Technology Development	New projects	Number of the new won project for execution phase
	Financing value	Values and found won for research and development
	Contracts value	Value of new or extended contracts
Procurement	Sourcing and negotiations	Value of Cost savings
		Cash flow improvement effect
HR Management	Staff selection and recruitment	New hires number
		Successful interviews number
	Training and development	Average trainings per employee
		Average trainings value per employee
Staff development, remuneration and retention	Attrition rate	
Company Infrastructure	Management team	EBT (Earnings Before Taxes)
	Planning and controlling	EBIT (Earnings Before Interests and Taxes)
	Finance and accounting	EBITDA (Earnings Before Interests, Taxes, Depreciation and Amortization)
	Finance and accounting	Netto Profit
	Legal	Fines and Penalties Paid (FPP)
	Public Relations	Total Cost of Social Responsibility related activities (CSR value)
	Quality	Number of audit findings
	Corporate Security	Internal Security Incidents
		Fatalities (Ft)
	Health and Safety Environment	Loss Time Injuries (LTI)
Non-LTI Injuries (Non-LTI)		
Accidental Spillages (AcSp)		

Methodology and approach

In order to perform the research, it was used the step-by-step multiple regression analysis, part of the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences - SPSS software. The research methodology was a survey-based questionnaire, the obtained data being processed using the SPSS program, version 23. The main source of obtaining the primary data was a multinational company, operating in Romania and focusing especially on the oil and gas industry. Through the involvement of their employees from various positions, specialists and experts as well, it was possible to obtain relevant information for conducting the research.

The questionnaire was used as a research tool, in order to obtain the data necessary for the study. It was designed in such a way that closed questions predominate, most of them being with multiple answers, respectively with answers in scale (using a scale of importance in five steps, varying between the extremes: very- and not at all). This allowed the respondents to choose from several predetermined answer options. The responses were then analyzed and processed using SPSS software.

From the different options available for performing a multiple regression, was used the stepwise variant. This is identical to the simple regression, with the mention that the difference consists in the use of several predictor variables, aiming to find some links that can explain the variance of the dependent variable.

The variables considered predictor were introduced in the model one by one, starting with the predictor variables having the highest correlation with the analyzed criteria. The test looked at whether each variable entered in the model contributed to its success, and if it was found that one or more of these variables did not significantly contribute to the success of the model, then these variables were automatically excluded by the program.

To exemplify the way in which the program was used, it can be seen how the analysis was performed, in order to determine the existence of any connection between the stages of the value chain and the

activities carried out within each stage, such as: inbound logistics, operations, outbound logistics, marketing, service and maintenance, technological development, procurement, human resources management and company infrastructure.

Correlations between the value chain's stages and the activities related to each stage

As a next research's step, were presented the links between the value chain's stages and the activities related to these stages, using the specific performance indicators.

The analysis aimed to determine the importance given to each stage, according to the importance level of the activities carried out within the value chain stages. For example, a complete analysis performed for the Input Logistics stage can be seen, according to Tables 2-7.

In the table 2, could be observe which variables were introduced into the analysis model.

Table 2. Variables Entered/Removed

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	ActivitN2: Inventariere: Grad_de_Imp		Stepwise (Criteria: Probability-of-F-to- enter <= .050, Probability-of-F-to- remove >= .100).

- a. Dependent Variable: Eta
- b. paLantValoareAN3: LI_Grad_de_Importanta

The table 3 indicates the variables that were not included in the regression analysis, not being considered as a significant predictor of the dependent variable.

Table 3. Excluded Variables

Model	Beta In	t	Sig.	Partial Correlation	Collinearity Statistics
					Tolerance
1 ActivitN2: Planif_Transp: Grad_de_Imp	.035 ^b	.184	.854	.019	.246
ActivitN2: Receptia: Grad_de_Imp	.019 ^b	.063	.950	.006	.101
ActivitN2: Depozitare: Grad_de_Imp	-.100 ^b	-.576	.566	-.058	.296

- a. Dependent Variable: EtapaLantValoareAN3: LI_Grad_de_Importanta
- b. Predictors in the Model: (Constant), ActivitN2: Inventariere: Grad_de_Imp

The result of the regression analysis is found in table 4, called Model Summary and reflects the fact that the predictor introduced in the regression equation, in our example being the Inventory activity, explains the variance of the dependent variable, in our case being Inbound Logistics, in proportion of 11.7 percent (R²adj = 0.117). In other words, the importance of the Inventory activity explains 11.7 percent of the variant of the dependent variable (Inbound Logistics).

Table 4. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.355 ^a	.126	.117	2.768	.126	14.256	1	99	.000

- a. Predictors: (Constant), ActivitN2: Inventariere: Grad_de_Imp

Table 5, named ANOVA, shows the existence of a statistically significant linear connection between the predictor variable (Inventory in our example) and the dependent variable (Inbound Logistics in our case).

Table 5. ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	109.241	1	109.241	14.256	.000 ^b
Residual	758.601	99	7.663		
Total	867.842	100			

a. Dependent Variable: EtapaLantValoareAN3: LI_Grad_de_Importanta

b. Predictors: (Constant), ActivitN2: Inventariere: Grad_de_Imp

Table 6 of this analysis, named Coefficients, contains the non-standardized Beta coefficients, respectively the standardized Beta coefficients for the exemplified variable predictor: Inventory. The values of “t” and “Sig” show that the independent variable has a significant contribution from the variance of importance given to the Input Logistics stage. The significance level in this case indicates the value of $0.000 < 0.05$ (being therefore below the maximum allowed significance threshold of 5%); so, the inclusion of the Inventory variable predictor in relation to the dependent variable (Inbound Logistics) is validated, being a significant variable.

Table 6. Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 (Constant)	2.666	.456		5.841	.000	1.760	3.571
ActivitN2: Inventariere: Grad_de_Imp	.775	.205	.355	3.776	.000	.368	1.183

a. Dependent Variable: EtapaLantValoareAN3: LI_Grad_de_Importanta

It can be noticed that the non-standardized coefficient’s value of the predictor taken into consideration is 0.775, and the standardized Beta coefficient is 0.355. The values recorded for the coefficients (both standardized and non-standardized) reflect the existence of a statistical connection between the Inbound Logistics dependent variable and the predictor variable considered (Inventory). In other words, it can be stated that the non-standardized Beta coefficient shows us how much the dependent variable changes, when the independent variable changes.

The significance is as follows: at an increase by one unit (from grade 2 to 3, or from 4 to 5, etc.), of the value of the Inventory variable, the value of the dependent variable (for our case was considered the importance of the Inbound Logistics) increases by 0.775. Thus, it will be close to one, which on a scale of 1 to 9 is the most important stage.

Based on the received answers and to elaborate the formula, in table 7 are presented the importance levels (grades), relevant to each analyzed activity of the value chain stages.

Table 7. Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
EtapaLantValoareAN3: LI_Grad_de_Importanta	4.04	2.946	101
ActivitN2: Planif_Transp: Grad_de_Imp	1.02	1.789	101
ActivitN2: Receptia: Grad_de_Imp	1.78	1.354	101
ActivitN2: Depozitare: Grad_de_Imp	2.43	.864	101
ActivitN2: Inventariere: Grad_de_Imp	1.77	1.348	101

Based on the previously presented information, it was possible to write the regression equation between the importance given to the analyzed stage and the calculated predictor. Therefore, the equation of the proposed conceptual model, when the non-standardized Beta coefficients are used, is the following:

$$Y = c + a_1 \cdot x_1 + a_2 \cdot x_2 + \dots + a_n \cdot x_n$$

Respectively, when using standardized scores, the proposed conceptual model's equation has the following form:

$$Y = A_1 \cdot X_1 + A_2 \cdot X_2 + \dots + A_n \cdot X_n$$

Where:

Y= represents the importance of the value chain stage;

c= represents the constant;

a= represents the non-standardized beta coefficient;

x= represents the importance grade of the considered predictor;

A= represents the value of the standardized beta coefficient;

X= represents the importance grade of of the considered predictor;

1, 2 ... n= represents the number of variables considered.

Discussion and conclusions

Based on the performed analyses regarding correlations existing between the stages of the value chain, it was found that the step-by-step multiple linear regression calculations indicated a statistically significant relationship in eight cases out of nine (representing 88.89 percent).

In case of the existing correlations related to the activities and operations, the obtained result has indicated a lower success rate than in the case of the value chain stages. Thus, for the core and support activities, together resulted 9 statistically significant regressions out of 34 simulations, which mean a 26,47 percent success rate).

The centralization of the received answers allowed the classification of the importance level of the value chain stages, as follows:

- 1st place: the most important value chain stage was considered the Company Infrastructure (with an average score of 2.75);
- the 2nd place, with an average score of 2.80 was assigned to the Operations stage;
- on the 3rd place is the Human Resources Management value chain stage, obtaining the average grade of 3.07;
- the Inbound Logistics stage was ranked on the 4th position, obtaining the average grade of 4.04;
- Technological Development ranks 5th, with an average grade of 4.09;
- the 6th place went to the Acquisitions stage, based on the average score of 4.18;
- the Marketing stage was ranked on the 7th position with an average score of 4.98;
- 8th place went to the Outbound Logistics stage, accumulating an average score of 5.09;
- and on the 9th place was ranked the Maintenance and Service stage, with an average score of 5.98, not accumulating any votes for the most important value chain stage.

The research's aim was to quantify the importance given by the respondents for each element presented in the model, taking into account all three levels of the analysis, as follows: stages, activities and operations.

These three dimensions were studied in terms of performance indicators, being considered the most relevant in this research. Even in the case of variables that do not seem to be statistically significant, it was nevertheless considered useful to observe them at least at the modeling and conceptual level, from

the perspective of the influence they may have on assessing the importance of activities during the supply chain stages.

Due to the non-random nature of the sampling methodology, the results obtained cannot be extrapolated, being representative only at the level of the investigated company, but the methodology used can be adapted for any other company, mentioning that certain activities or operations can be found or not in their activity portfolio. Respectively, certain specific operations may have different weights and importance, depending on several company-specific factors. In case of any other further research, it would be possible to reduce the limitations of the current study and to introduce new elements in the performance analysis of the value chain stages.

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